

Effect of different irrigation regimes on some agronomic characteristics of indica rice, Varanasi, India.

Treatment	Grain yield ^a (g/hill)	Harvest index ^a (%)	Relative efficiency of nutrient recovery (%)	
			Nitrogen	Phosphorus
I ₁ Continuous saturation at maximum water-holding capacity	20.3 d	52 b	100	100
I ₂ Saturation during vegetative + flooding during reproductive stage	29.4 b	58 a	147	155
I ₃ Flooding during vegetative stage + saturation during reproductive stage	23.4 c	43 d	124	142
I ₄ Continuous flooding (5 cm depth)	32.9 a	46 c	155	113
Significance	*	*	–	–
C.D. at 5% level	2.13	2.61		

^aMean values with the same letter do not differ significantly.

butrium between the growth rates in the vegetative and reproductive stages. But although flooding at the vegetative stage increased the rice plant's vegetation

appreciably, saturation during the development of reproductive organs caused a setback (see table). ■

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. contributions are subject to editing and abridgement to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.

Soil and crop management

Blue-green algae in deepwater rice in Mali, West Africa

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Epiphytic algae on rice may contribute to the fertility of paddy soils and may be important where fertilizers are not used. Their presence in deepwater rice has been reported in Bangladesh. This

article reports the presence of blue-green algae (BGA) in deepwater rice in Africa.

Stem sections of variety Mogo, *Oryza glaberrima*, including nodal roots and leaf sheaths, were removed from a field of deepwater rice near Mopti, Mali, on 10 October 1978. The water was 165 cm deep. The stem sections were preserved in 2% formalin (39% formaldehyde).

The algae from both the sedimented samples and various parts of the rice plant were examined. The former served as a check for the occurrence and

relative abundance of the algae in the latter's habitat. The algae were observed directly through a compound microscope. Temporary mounts were prepared in lactophenol blue from a 2- to 3-mm² pieces of leaf sheaths and leaf blades, and from pieces of nodal roots about 1-2 mm long. The cover slips were later sealed with melted paraffin and kept in the herbarium of the UPLB.

Twenty-six species of algae were identified from the material. The table lists the BGA and indicates their relative abundance. BGA constituted the greatest algal bulk in the sample. Of the eight species of BGA identified, seven are nitrogen fixers: *Anabaena torulosa*, *A. vaginicola*, *Cylindrospermum licheniforme*, *Gloeocapsa quaternata*, *Gloeotrichia natans*, *Hapalosiphon stuhlmanii*, and *Nostoc* sp.

The chlorophytes were well represented (13 species) but only *Bulbochaete* sp. and *Oedogonium* sp. were present in significant numbers. Five species of euglenophytes and diatoms occurred in low numbers. ■

Blue-green algae observed on deepwater rice Mogo, in Mopti, Mali, West Africa.

Species	Relative abundance ^a		
	Leaf/leaf sheath	Nodal roots	Sediment
<i>Anabaena torulosa</i> (Carm.) Lag.			++++
<i>A. vaginicola</i> Fritsch et Rich	+++	+++	+++
<i>Chroococcus limneticus</i> Lemm.	++	++	++
<i>Cylindrospermum licheniforme</i> (Bory) Kuetz.	+++	++	++
<i>Gloeocapsa quaternata</i> (Breb.) Kuetz.	+		+
<i>Gloeotrichia natans</i> (Hedw.) Rabh.	++++	+++	++++
<i>Hapalosiphon stuhlmanii</i> Hieron.	++++	+++	++++
<i>Nostoc</i> sp.	++++		++

^a++++ = abundant, +++ = moderate, ++ = rare, + = very rare.